

Zika Virus Disease: A Review

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INTRODUCTION :

The mosquito-borne Zika virus (ZIKV) belongs to the Flavivirus genus, which is part of the Flaviviridae family. ZIKV is spread by various mosquito species, including *Aedes africanus*, *Aedes aegypti*, *Aedes albopictus*, and *Aedes hensilli*, just like other flaviviruses^{1,2,3}.

In April 1947, the virus was first isolated from a sentinel rhesus monkey by British scientists working at the Yellow Fever Research Laboratory in the Zika Forest near Lake Victoria, Uganda and was given the name as Zika virus and was transmitted predominantly by the mosquito vector, *Aedes aegypti*^{4,5}. The first human cases of Zika virus (ZIKV) were discovered in 1952, and Zika outbreaks have been documented in tropical Africa, Southeast Asia, and the Pacific Islands since then⁵. Before 2007, there had been at least 14 documented cases of Zika, with many more likely to have occurred but not reported⁵. In 2007, Yap Island Micronesia experienced the first major ZIKV outbreak outside of Africa, with about three-quarters of the population over the age of three suspected of being sick⁶. The major mosquito species involved in the transmission of ZIKV in this occurrence was *Aedes hensilli*, and infection symptoms included rash, arthralgia, and conjunctivitis⁶. Following that, in 2013 and 2014, ZIKV spread to French Polynesia with over 29,000 infections reported^{6,7}. ZIKV first appeared in the Americas in March 2015, and as of the end of January 2016, autochthonous ZIKV circulation had been reported in more than 20 countries or territories in South, Central, and North America, as well as the Caribbean, with an outbreak reported in November in West Africa (Cape Verde)⁸. The World Health Organization declared Zika virus a Global Health Emergency of International Concern on 1st February 2016⁹. In India ZIKV was first reported in 2017, with significant outbreaks in 2018¹⁰. In July 2021, ZIKV is again reported from Kerala.

TRANSMISSION :

Zika can be transmitted

1. Through mosquito bites¹¹
2. From a pregnant woman to her fetus¹²
3. Through sex¹³
4. Through blood transfusion¹⁴
5. Through organ transplantation^{15,16}.

CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS :

The majority of ZIKV infections (50 to 80 percent) are asymptomatic^{11,17}. A rash, low-grade fever, arthralgia and myalgia, and conjunctivitis are all symptoms of symptomatic ZIKV infection, which has an incubation period of 3 to 14 days and can last up to 1 week¹⁸. Complications are uncommon, but when they do happen, they are serious and sometimes fatal. Acute ZIKV infection has identical symptoms in people of all ages, both sexes, including pregnant women¹⁹. Although ZIKV has a broad cellular tropism, the neurologic problems that result from a post-infectious immune response or direct viral neurotropism are the most striking component of the clinical manifestation (Figure1). Vertical infection results in microcephaly with brain and eye anomalies, while adult infection results in Guillain-Barre syndrome (GBS) and meningoencephalitis²⁰.

Figure 1 : Zika Virus Transmission and Clinical Features.

ZIKV-Associated Guillain–Barré Syndrome

The risk of ZIKV-associated Guillain–Barré syndrome is estimated to be 2 to 3 cases per 10,000 ZIKV infections, which is comparable to the risk of campylobacter infection^{21,22}. The time elapsed between the onset of the antecedent illness and the onset of the Guillain–Barré syndrome is 5 to 10 days, raising the possibility of a contributory parainfectious process²³. With ZIKV-associated Guillain–Barré syndrome, acute inflammatory demyelinating polyneuropathy, acute motor axonal neuropathy, and the Miller–Fisher syndrome (a subset of the Guillain–Barré syndrome characterised by ophthalmoplegia, ataxia, and areflexia) have been observed, but the relative proportions of these subtypes vary across studies and regions^{23,24,25}. Several case series revealed that the prognosis of ZIKV-associated Guillain–Barré syndrome was similar to that of Guillain–Barré syndrome caused by other infectious or noninfectious processes; however, findings from a case–control study suggest that ZIKV-associated Guillain–Barré syndrome causes more morbidity and cranial neuropathy^{23,26}. ZIKV infection has also been linked to other autoimmune disorders such as thrombocytopenic purpura.

Congenital Zika Syndrome

ZIKV causes a spectrum of foetal and birth defects that extends beyond microcephaly and is distinct from other congenital infections in the fact that its pathologic manifestations are primarily limited to the central nervous system, as was discovered early in the microcephaly epidemic^{27,28}. Fetal brain disruption sequence, a condition caused by partial brain disruption during gestation with subsequent collapse of the foetal skull caused by decreased intracranial hydrostatic pressure; subcortical calcifications; pyramidal and extrapyramidal signs; chorioretinal atrophy and focal pigmented mottling of the retina; and congenital contractures that appear to be caused by a neurogenic complication are all prominent features of congenital Zika syndrome²⁹ (Table 1). Although these anomalies have been observed in other congenital infections, they appear to be more commonly associated with congenital Zika syndrome²⁸.

Newborns of ZIKV-infected mothers have a 5 to 14 percent risk of congenital Zika syndrome and a 4 to 6 percent risk of ZIKV-associated microcephaly^{30,31}. A study involving pregnant women in Rio de Janeiro used a broader definition for ZIKV-associated outcomes and found that 42 percent of fetuses and infants exposed to the virus had adverse outcomes³¹. Although ZIKV infection can occur in any trimester of pregnancy, infections in the first trimester are more likely to result in congenital Zika syndrome^{30,31}. Pesticides, toxins, medications, and maternal immunizations have not been identified as risk factors³². Neonatal mortality in the first week of life may be as high as 4 to 7% among infants with congenital Zika syndrome and better estimates of neonatal mortality after the first week of life are required³¹.

Table 1: Salient Features of Congenital Zika Syndrome⁴¹

Lesion Type	Manifestations
Structural lesions	
Fetal brain disruption sequence*	Severe microcephaly, premature closure of fontanel, collapsed skull, overlapping sutures, redundant scalp skin
Brain abnormalities	Cortical atrophy with decreased myelination, cerebellar hypoplasia. Neuronal migration disorder-lissencephaly, agyria, pachygyria, polymicrogyria, heterotopia, dysgenesis of corpus callosum; Calcifications, mainly subcortical*; Ventriculomegaly, increased posterior fossa and pericerebral spaces
Ocular abnormalities	Pigmented retinal mottling*, chorioretinal atrophy*, macular scarring, glaucoma, optic nerve atrophy and abnormalities, intraocular calcifications; Microphthalmia, anophthalmia; Iris coloboma, lens subluxation, cataract
Congenital contractures	Arthrogryposis, talipes equinovarus, hip dislocation
Intrauterine growth restriction	
Functional lesions	
Seizures	
Pyramidal or extrapyramidal Abnormalities*	Body tone abnormalities (mainly hypertonia), swallowing disorder, movement abnormalities (Dyskinesia, dystonia), hyperexcitability, impatient crying, sleep disorders
Neurodevelopmental abnormalities	Visual impairment (strabismus, nystagmus, vision loss) Hearing loss or deafness Developmental delay

*Lesions are rarely observed in other congenital infections

DIAGNOSIS

The clinical manifestations of acute ZIKV infection are nonspecific, thus nucleic acid testing or serologic testing are used to make a definitive diagnosis (Table 2).

Table 2: Diagnostic and Clinical Evaluation of Zika Virus Exposure⁴¹

Patient Population and ZIKV Exposure	ZIKV Laboratory Investigations (Schedule)		Other Evaluations (Schedule)
	Nucleic Acid Testing	IgM Serologic Testing	
General population			
Uncomplicated ZIKV infection	Not recommended	Not recommended	Not recommended
Possible associated Guillain-Barré syndrome	Paired serum and urine; testing of cerebrospinal fluid should be considered	Serum; testing of cerebrospinal fluid should be considered	Nerve conduction studies; cerebrospinal fluid chemical analysis
Presenting for preconception screening	Not recommended	Not recommended	Not recommended
Pregnant women			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possible ZIKV exposure; symptomatic • Possible recent ZIKV exposure; no ongoing exposure; asymptomatic • Possible ZIKV exposure; fetus has findings on ultrasound consistent with congenital ZIKV infection* 	Paired serum and urine (ASAP, up to 12 weeks after onset of illness)	Serum (ASAP, up to 12 weeks after onset of illness)	Ultrasonography (at 18-22 weeks of gestation); Serial ultrasonography (every 3-4 weeks); No universal recommendation for amniocentesis
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possible ongoing ZIKV exposure; asymptomatic 	Paired serum and urine (at initial visit and during each trimester)	Not recommended	Ultrasonography (at 18-22 weeks of gestation); Serial ultrasonography (every 3-4 weeks); No universal recommendation for amniocentesis
New-borns			
No findings of congenital Zika syndrome; mother had possible ZIKV exposure (not laboratory-confirmed) or was not tested	Not recommended	Not recommended	Physical and neurologic examination at birth and at each follow-up visit
No findings of congenital Zika syndrome; mother had laboratory-confirmed ZIKV exposure during pregnancy	Paired serum and urine (within 2 days after birth)	Serum (within 2 days after birth)	Physical and neurologic examination at birth; Head circumference retested 24 hours after birth; Ultrasonography of the head by 1 month of age; consider MRI if available; Ophthalmologic examination by 1 month of age; AABR testing by 1 month of age
Findings of congenital Zika syndrome; mother had possible ZIKV exposure during pregnancy	Paired serum and urine (within 2 days after birth)	Serum (within 2 days after birth)	Same as for an infant without congenital Zika syndrome findings who is born to a mother with laboratory-confirmed exposure during pregnancy; Screening for other causes of fetal abnormalities (genetic, infectious, toxic, or metabolic)
Stillbirth or neonatal death; mother had possible or laboratory-confirmed ZIKV exposure during pregnancy	Placental and fetal tissues	Not recommended	Repeat serologic test in mother if previous results were negative; Autopsy

* Amniotic fluid testing of placental and fetal tissues should be considered

ZIKV: Zika Virus; IgM: Immunoglobulin M; ASAP: As Soon As Possible; MRI: Magnetic Resonance Imaging; AABR: Automated Auditory Brainstem Response

Whole blood or serum samples obtained during the first days of illness should be tested for nucleic acids. Given the potentially prolonged duration of ZIKV RNA in these fluids, testing paired blood and urine samples obtained within 2 weeks of the onset of illness is recommended^{33,34}. Although the detection of ZIKV RNA provides conclusive evidence of infection, a negative result does not rule out the possibility of infection^{33,35}. A positive nucleic acid test indicates the presence of ZIKV RNA but does not always indicate the presence of an infectious virus. False positive results from cross-reactivity in people who have been exposed to other flaviviruses complicate serodiagnosis³³.

MANAGEMENT :

No antiviral agents have been approved by regulatory agencies for the treatment of ZIKV infection, thus supportive care is used in the clinical management of acute ZIKV infection³⁶.

ZIKV-associated Guillain–Barré syndrome is treated in the same way as classic Guillain–Barré syndrome, with therapeutic plasma exchange or intravenous immune globulin³⁷. Infant care recommendations are stratified based on clinical and imaging findings in the infant as well as laboratory evidence of ZIKV infection in the mother during pregnancy³⁸. Infants with congenital ZIKV infection require care from a multidisciplinary team that monitors complications, includes a developmental specialist, and provides early intervention services³⁸. Family and supportive services are critical components in the care of infants infected with ZIKV³⁸.

- There is no specific medicine for Zika virus.
- Treat the symptoms.
- Plenty of rest is advised.
- Encourage drinking fluids to prevent dehydration.
- Give medicine such as acetaminophen to reduce fever and pain.
- Do not give aspirin and other non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) until dengue can be ruled out to reduce the risk of bleeding.
- No vaccine is currently available.

PREVENTION :

1. Protect from mosquito bites: Once a week, empty and scrub, turn over, cover, or throw out items that hold water. Tightly cover water storage containers. Use larvicides to kill larvae in containers of water that cannot be emptied and will not be used for drinking. Use an insect spray made to kill mosquitoes in areas where they rest. If you have a septic tank, repair cracks or gaps. Use window and door screens. Use air conditioning when possible. Use a repellent with one of the following active ingredients: DEET, picaridin, IR3535, or oil of lemon eucalyptus, para-menthane-diol, or 2-undecanone. Cover up exposed skin. Wear long-sleeved shirts and long pants. Treat clothing and gear. Use permethrin to treat clothing and gear or buy pre-treated items. For babies and children: Dress your child in clothing that covers arms and legs. For children older than 2 months, use insect repellent on exposed skin. Cover crib, stroller, and baby carrier with mosquito netting.

2. Preventing sexual transmission: Condoms can reduce the chance of getting Zika from sex. Condoms should be used from start to finish, every time during vaginal, anal, and oral sex and the sharing of sex toys. People with a partner who travelled to an area with risk of Zika can use condoms or not have sex. If the traveller is female: For at least 8 weeks after return, or after start of symptoms or diagnosis³⁹. If the traveller is male: For at least 6 months after return, or after start of symptoms or diagnosis. People living in an area with risk of Zika can use condoms or not have sex.

3. Preventing transmission in pregnancy: Prevention of congenital Zika syndrome relies on avoidance of infection during pregnancy or postponement of pregnancy⁴⁰.

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